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Kerala- Gulf Migration Corridor: Women's Labour and Gender Stereotypes

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ABSTRACT

It is worth noticing that in recent years, female labour migration to the Gulf has contributed abundantly in the development spectrum of the Kerala state. The emergence of growing international need for domestic workers and care workers demanded supply of cheap labour in the capitalist global economy. The socio-cultural association of women with domestic and care work often emerges as a major shaping influence on female migration. Kerala state has seen a rise in the number of female migrants traveling to the Gulf for jobs as professional nurses and domestic workers in the past many decades. This paper will analyse the gendering aspect of female migration from Kerala to the Arab Gulf, having a major focus on their gender role attributions and labour challenges in both home and host societies.

KEY WORDS: Kerala- Gulf Migration, Gender, Domestic Workers, Emigrant Nurses

INTRODUCTION

For many centuries, Kerala, a state in the Malabar Coast region of southwest India, has experienced waves of *in* and *out* migration. The state has consistently been a popular destination for immigrants, including Jews, Syrian Christians, Arabs, Konkini brahmins, and others. In the preface to *Migration and Economic Development of Kerala* (1988), KC Zachariah notes that one of the main causes of Keralaites' current widespread migration to different regions of the world may be their ancient legacy of interaction with diverse traders and international communities. The globalization period has brought about the creation of a world in which the processes of convergence and movement have united all economies. The massive advancements in technology, the evolving industrial system, and the ensuing economic revolution all served as reflections of the overall phenomenon. International migration has been significantly impacted by economic globalization,

which promotes free trade across boundaries. It allowed citizens of developing and under developed nations to achieve economic stability in abroad rather than in their own country and thereby marked a significant turning point in the history of global migration.

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Before the 1940s, Kerala was not known for its outmigration. Keralites left their home region in quest of a better life due to the Second World War, poverty, and other issues. The state used to attract more residents from nearby states up till the fourth decade of the 20th century. Many people, particularly those from the Madras Presidency, found significant work in the Travancore-Cochin states (Zacharia et al. 13). Due to the unique characteristics of the region and the hospitable attitude of the rulers toward the migrants, the Travancore-Cochin states were mostly contained the characteristics of “in migration” prior to World War II. However, during the war time, a large number of Keralites were recruited for jobs including clerks, soldiers, military officers, and other positions in the overseas. Many people were able to move out from their “home” because to this. Out migration, that time was limited to the Malabar region (a portion of the Madras Presidency that was directly governed by the British) until the creation of the integrated state. This migration was significantly influenced by the historical, geographical, and other structural aspects of Malabar. The downfall of the rural economy in the region resulted in a financial crisis which brought a major transformation in the social and economic spectrum. The Gulf remittances, eventually, contributed to the revival of the conventional economy that had been collapsed. Later, a multitude of options beyond the boundaries became available with the merging of the Travancore-Cochin states with Malabar. Numerous other causes, such as the population growth and societal advancements in education, also contributed to the acceleration of migration. The effects of this trend began to affect every facet of state life in the last few decades.

Over the last several decades, migration has spread so much that it now affects every socioeconomic segment of the state. In addition to increasing in volume, migration has had a noticeable impact on the social behaviour of the state's population since the 1970s. Since the oil boom, there has been a significant exodus of skilled, semi-skilled, and unskilled labourers, primarily to the GCC countries—the United Arab Emirates, Saudi Arabia, Oman, Kuwait, Qatar, and Bahrain. Migration through ‘illegal’ channels was occurring even prior to the oil boom; the huge exodus did not occur until after that (Shibnu 120). According to Zachariah et al. (2004), the two main categories of mass migration to GCC nations for employment are contract migration and settlement migration. The former is characterized by circulation and transitoriness. Indians are the

“quintessential citizens of the gulf,” according to Neha Vora, who made this claim in her book *Impossible Citizens: Dubai's Indian Diaspora* (2013) (Vora 1). The majority of the Indian diaspora in the Gulf are from the state of Kerala (Jain 102). The most dynamic force driving Kerala's economy since the final part of the 20th century has been Gulf migration, which has a significant impact on the state's labor market, investment, savings, consumption, income distribution, etc. Out of all the countries, the United Arab Emirates is the friendliest to emigrants from Kerala, second place goes to Saudi Arabia (Zachariah and Rajan 10). Keralites, who have adopted an “out going out look” anticipate better job prospects, greater pay, and improved living conditions in their new country. The Malayali diaspora community residing in the Gulf, however, has a big influence on Kerala society's sociocultural, political, and economic spheres.

Women Migration to the GCC Countries

The start of the widespread relocation of Indian women workers to Gulf regions was facilitated by the oil boom. The majority of migrant care workers in developed and developing countries, such as housemaids, nurses, and other domestic workers, were South Asian women. When compared to other Indian states, Kerala sent the majority of its women abroad to work in these professions. Kerala nurses have been hopping across borders since the 1940s, seeking better chances, better labour conditions, and more pay. Majority of the female migrant nurses from India are from Kerala, primarily from Syrian Christian families residing in Central Travancore, which is Kerala's nursing powerhouse, which includes the districts of Kottayam, Pathanamthitta, and Idukki. Malayali nurses had already relocated to Europe, mostly to Germany, Italy, Switzerland, and England, before the Gulf boom and the globalization era, to meet the nursing shortage that emerged following World War II (Benyamin 39). Nuns were also sent as caretakers into many of these nations during the post-war era through Catholic churches. Subsequently, Singapore, Africa, America, Ireland, Australia, and the Middle East saw an increase in the trend of nurse migration. Women make up 14% of Kerala's emigrant population, according to the Centre for Development Studies' Kerala Migration Survey, 2014. In the nursing industry specifically in 2014, there were 85 percent of nurses working overseas in correspondence to 100 nurses in Kerala (Zachariah and Rajan 16). North America (Canada and the USA), the

UK, Ireland, Australia, and later the GCC countries are considered to be significant and even preferred destinations for Indian nurses among the industrialized regions.

In the 1940s, around 6000 Indian nurses, primarily from Kerala's Catholic population, travelled to Germany to meet the shortage of health workers after the World War II (Gottschlich 2). There were not enough German nurses to meet the increasing demand that the War had caused. Due to their close ties to Germany at this time, Christian missionaries in Kerala played an important role in the recruitment of nurses from their region. The church assisted in creating a personal and community network that sped up the migration process. The women who crossed borders struggled to fit into the competitive labour market and saw the ugly face of sexism and racism despite achieving economic independence and personal freedom (Mariam 67). The Gulf countries have been in need of additional health workers as well as skilled, semi-skilled, and unskilled labourers for a variety of industries since the 1960s, particularly with the growth of oil economies. The employment problems in the homeland gradually led to a major exodus of nurses, particularly female nurses, who left their jobs in search of better jobs and lives. Their selection of location was influenced by several factors. They discovered that Arab nations, particularly Kuwait and Saudi Arabia, were the most sought-after locations since, in the past, they conducted interviews in India and covered all costs, including airfare, rather than requesting sponsorships. Many girls who enrolled in private institutes' B.Sc. Nursing programs and take out loans are compelled to relocate abroad in order to repay their liabilities. According to recent surveys, Kerala's nursing migration is slowing down as a result of the political and economic unrest.

Following the oil boom, there was a large-scale migration of women to the GCC countries. The growing demand for house workers is one of the main factors pushing the feminisation of labour migration in past decades in many countries including the Arab Gulf. The need for domestic help has increased dramatically in the GCC countries, drawing in a lot of people from third-world countries. Among women migrants from India, domestic workers are disproportionately subjected to abuse in many destination countries including the Arab Gulf. The struggle is reflected in each phase of the migration cycle, including the beginning with the decision to migrate. Thimothi et.al (2022) observes that "factors like lack of reliable information on migration

processes, stringent control imposed by the State on women's mobility and continuing dependence on recruitment agencies, increasing vulnerabilities women encounter in the migration cycle" (2). The 2015 ILO study makes it abundantly evident that female semi-skilled and unskilled workers in the GCC countries are not free to switch sponsors, and they are frequently the targets of physical and sexual exploitation, travel document seizure, and other abuses.

Women's Labour and Gender Stereotyping

In India, women's migration, initially was a secondary phenomenon, with men being the primary source of motivation for women to leave their homes. Many noted that, although it also made some economic contributions in its later stages, the early phase of migration in India produced a "social" output rather than an "economic" one. In addition to the typical push and pull variables, two additional factors that contributed to this extraordinary rate of female migration were the growing need for female workers and the growing awareness of women's equality in society. An essential influence was also performed by the developed community networks and the improved social capital. The majority of Keralites formed their social lives in the host country through the transnational institutional channel of the church. That time, nurses were stigmatized as sexually provocative women or the one who carry a "dirty" profession, demonstrating the severe caste, class, and gender biases that prevailed at that point. The perception of seeing nursing profession as "dirty" gradually got changed when women entered the workforce and actively participate in social settings. Coming from a place where a women cares or touch a stranger is seen as a 'sin', they broke the socially stigmatized gender norms and boundaries by mingling and treating a number of men in their new work places. By being the first to immigrate and establish their dominance in the economic realm, nurses challenged the stereotype of immigrants as predominantly male. They questioned the male-dominated, established structures of society like the "family," the "church," and others while claiming their economic and social independence through the newly developed discourse and narratives.

As he explains his theories of power, gender and labour, Raewyn Connell discusses gender ideology, how politics operate in workplaces, and how masculine power exercises control, power, and oppression over female labour (quoted in Mariam 12). Connell coined the phrase "gender regime" to describe the gender structures that

permeate social institutions and ultimately govern labour and power. Since men predominate in the home and church, the historically established gender regime changes when they migrate first. The migrated nurses' spouses made an effort to regain their lost influence in the home country within the church and family. Sheba Mariam claims that the traditionally "marginalized men," who once enjoyed absolute authority in Kerala society and their native territory, now search for space in the emigrated area to meet their needs on an economic, cultural, and religious level. "Home" is the safest place in a xenophobic culture (Mariam 18). The migrant women, particularly those who were relocated to industrialized Western nations, were able to preserve this safe haven by conforming to gender norms even when they achieved economic independence.

Emigrant nurses' experiences are related to their caste, class, religion, racial marginalization, sexual orientation, and xenophobia. Globalization affects the diasporic formations of today, and as a result of that, the interests of the cultural and social hegemonic forces that gave rise to inequality and individual differences determine the internal structure of the diaspora. The strength of transnational communities is determined by these diasporic hegemonies, and the connection they created is governed by sociopolitical and material variables that exist there. It was clear when conceptualizing and theorizing diasporic discourses that the traditional notion of "diaspora," which is primarily studied through binary concepts like home/host land, displacement/settlement, is always cantered around masculine subjects or considers men to be the primary agents of diasporic formations. The concept of 'Gendering Diaspora' emerged from the recognition that the term "diaspora" encompasses a broader range of socio-political and cultural meanings that cannot be limited to a certain masculine topic. Within this field of research, a new feminist scholarship was made possible by this insight.

In a globalized environment, labour relations produce the relationship between gender and geographic mobility. The global political and economic landscapes of both countries have a lasting influence on the gendered views of diasporic subjectivity in the host land. The structural dynamic of gender is always contradictory in "nursing" profession. The belief that the term "gender" is exclusively connected to women is a widely held fallacy, while the term actually refers to the social connotations attached to sexual differences. In addition to influencing possibilities on an individual basis, gender also structures social interactions among

individuals of all sexual orientations. In society, gender relations are defined by a variety of frameworks. In his paper "Women in a Women's Job: The Gendered Experiences of Nurses," Sam Porter outlines the three basic ways in which gender and nursing are related. First, the field is stigmatized as "women's work." He notes that it is problematic to categorize nursing as a "feminine" vocation and to attribute to it traits such as sacrifice, care, patience, hygiene, etc. Second, the predominance of elite masculinity contributes to high levels of occupational inequality, authority, control, and coercion in the workplace. Thirdly, gender "overdetermines inter-occupational inequalities" due to the sexual division of labour (Porter 511). Florence Nightingale led a group of nurses who organized to work at a British military hospital during the Crimean War fifty years ago. Because of her intervention, nursing was seen as a respectable career for women, bringing about significant changes to Victorian moral culture (Anthony 121). In comparison to female nurses at that time, the percentage of male nurses was less than 10% (qtd.in Porter). A new paradigm for the nursing profession was created by Florence Nightingale's training school in 1860, and it was this model that popularized the idea that nursing is a feminine vocation (121).

Among women migrants from India, domestic workers are disproportionately subjected to abuse in many destination countries including the Arab Gulf. The struggle is reflected in each phase of the migration cycle, including the beginning with the decision to migrate. They migrate primarily for economic reasons, albeit occasionally for social ones as well. Their narratives reveal the stark realities of the sponsorship or "kafala" system, which links the legal status of migrant workers to their employers, rendering them vulnerable to abuse and exploitation. In the case of domestic workers also, it is recognized as more and more women centred profession. The majority of female domestic workers that migrate to the Gulf region are members of the lower middle class, and their job is to either fulfil or replace the gender roles of other women (Labadie and Jackson 70). One can observe the global care chain phenomena here where the female domestic workers transferring their burdens of social reproduction to other female members in the family so that they can take the same gender roles in employer's household in return of salary. Paradoxically, Fitzpatrick and Kelley mentions in their article, the "sending states and husbands of the migrant domestics, like the destination states and husbands in employing households, appear unwilling to assume any

substantial portion of the social reproductive tasks that are the impediment (at the sending end) and also the magnet (at the receiving end) of the maid trade” (51). In the past few decades, many semi-skilled- unskilled Kerala women have made the decision to relocate on their own, leaving behind partners or family members, in search of better opportunities. Their financial dominance didn't significantly altered their gender role attributions both in homeland and the host land.

CONCLUSION

The feminization of migration is an important aspect of the new development of the international migration. The increased demand for female care workers in the GCC countries in the past decades attracted a lot of people from the third world countries. The way the gender power system functions with regard to Kerala migrant women workers is paradoxical. They questioned the economic and ideological dominance of patriarchy in the family and, in one sense, challenged the traditional moral-patriarchal norms that were in place. On the other hand, they were socially and culturally restricted to hierarchical institutions, whether in their homeland or their host country. They were somewhat free from the direct rule of male forces outside the home, the universal categorisation of women as inferior subjects made no exception for them. Malayali Emigrant workers, especially in the 'care' professions in the Gulf, faced discrimination even after taking care of everything at home, and their reliance on social institutions like family and religion masked the financial independence they achieved. Despite their great demand and level of skill, they encounter a range of difficulties and forms of exploitation at the workplace. Even though the existing gendered practices and discourse gets questioned in the immigration process, their traditional gender roles in home and community sphere remained the same.

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Authors' Contributions

Anagha conceptualized and designed the study, also drafted the manuscript. Dr.Sajaudeen contributed to the thorough review and editing of the final manuscript. Both the authors provided their critical input on the paper, read and approved the final paper. Anagha takes responsibility as a guarantor for this research article.

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